

Security Challenges and Secondary School Teachers' Effectiveness in Osun State, Nigeria

AUTHOR(S): ODEDIJI, Kehinde Morufdeen
And
OLOFIN, Samuel Oluwaseyi (Ph.D)

Abstract

The study examined security challenges and secondary school teachers' effectiveness in Osun State. Specifically, the study examined the relationship between variables of security challenges such as terrorism, cultism and school safety, and secondary school teachers' effectiveness. The descriptive survey research and correlational research designs were used in this study. The population consisted of all teachers in public secondary schools in Osun State, Nigeria. The sample for this study consisted of 240 teachers in 24 public secondary schools which were selected using multi - stage sampling procedure. Two self-designed research instruments tagged "Security Challenges Questionnaire (SCQ)" and "Teachers' Effectiveness Questionnaire (TEQ)" were used to collect data for the study. The validity of the instruments was ensured through face and content validity. The reliability of the instruments was determined by using test re-test reliability method. The data collected through the instruments were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings of the study revealed that there was no significant relationship between terrorism and secondary school teachers' effectiveness ($r = 0.011$) but relationship existed between cultism and secondary school teachers' effectiveness ($r = -0.412, p < 0.05$), and between school safety and secondary school teachers' effectiveness ($r = 0.607, p < 0.05$). Sequel to the findings of this study, it was concluded that security challenges such as cultism and school safety determined the effectiveness of teachers in secondary schools. It was recommended among others that school management should install Closed Circuit Television (CCTV) at strategic places to monitor activities of staff and students for possible discovery of criminal events within the school compound.

IJARBAS

Accepted 5 September 2022
Published 31 January 2023
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7644490

Keywords: Terrorism, Cultism, School Safety, Teachers' Effectiveness,

About Author

Author(s):

ODEDIJI, Kehinde Morufdeen

Department of Educational management
Faculty of Education,
Ekiti State University, Ado – Ekiti, Nigeria.
odedijikehinde@gmail.com

and

OLOFIN, Samuel Oluwaseyi (Ph.D)

Advocate Educational Consult, Nigeria.
engineersam2003@yahoo.com

Introduction

Effectiveness denotes the knowledge, performance and dexterity in teaching and learning (Meiers, 2007), so it involves teachers' capacity to handle the teaching and learning process from the planning to the evaluation phases. Hence, National Policy of Education (2013) defined teachers' effectiveness as the indulgent of essential education, learners, curriculum development, lesson plans, instructional teaching and learning process, learning evaluation, and the potential developments of the students.

Teachers' effectiveness is an indicator utilized to depict teacher efficacy and competence with considerations to the correlation between the features of teaching acts and their implication they have on the educational upshot in the course of classroom teaching. Oluchukwu (2010) expressed that effectiveness is a resultant effect of the internally of three types of resources and they include physicals, financial and human resources. He opined that in order to enhance and improve effectiveness, human must be well understood and affected positively.

It appears some secondary school teachers no longer place great priority on their primary role, which is teaching (Olofin & Olojo, 2022). In the aspect of teaching, the researcher observed that some teachers appear not to be punctual in the classrooms. It was observed that some teachers no longer use relevant instructional materials for teaching, some of them are used to obsolete method of teaching while some appear not to have mastery of the subject matter and some teachers seem not to have total control of the class during teaching.

Effectiveness according to Oluchukwu (2010) has to do with result measurement and he described performance measures as those ratings used in evaluating employee, which include teachers' service delivery, teacher student relationship, changing teaching/learning process and above all, students' academic performance on the job is value to the organization and this is determined through teacher effectiveness.

Ornstein and Lunenburg (2008) identify that the teacher must have a thorough grasp of the subject he teaches. Effective learning demands that the teacher must possess a solid knowledge of his/her subject. The research justifications among others advance the universal knowledge of the community; it is a crucial element in effectual teaching; augments the exercise of a meticulous discipline in the actual humanity of contact; and it is essential to continue one's personal discipline or one's individual self-esteem (Lertputtarak, 2008). Staff promotions are centred wholly on research publication (Bassegy & Bassegy, 2008). It amplifies the academic staff rank to the highest level of professors and augments the capacity of the knowledge, teaching competences and aptitude to converse efficiently with the students thus turning out to be a key spin on which the tertiary institution relies (Ebeniza & Ukegbu, 2015). Teachers' effectiveness according to Okolocha and Onyeneke (2013) tends to be associated with some factors. These factors are individual's ability and skills to perform the job, his level of motivation, the operating personnel policies and the organizational climate tend to operate jointly and simultaneously to determine an individual's or teacher's degree of productivity on the job. It is only when the factors are positively and favourably oriented to the individual (teacher) that one can expect high effectiveness.

Effective teaching possibly will embrace high creativity level in analyzing, amalgamating and knowledge presentation in innovative and efficient manners. It ought to implant in the students the capability to be methodical, academically inquisitive, ethnically conscious, employable and competent of headship. Okolie (2014) noted that teaching is the greatly individualized action, and the learner-teacher dealing is a powerful human rapport that covers a broad array of qualities and manners. The teaching programme quality cannot go up beyond her teachers' quality.

Security according to Nwabueze (2016) refers to safety, freedom from danger or risk. There are standards put in place to make the school situation secure. A place where there is security is a place of safety (Trump, 2010). Trump (2010) sees security as the stamina of every culture, and it is inevitably concurrent with social, financial, didactic, political, and civilizing development. Security challenges are vital matters that can affect all facets of life. The indication of a safe school is the presence and implementation of planned policies which are well-drawn policies of the protection that should be given to the stakeholders within the school, be it learners, teacher or school managers.

The secondary school has an alienable right and responsibility to secure itself, while the students and teachers have confidence in its care (Oni, 2019). The school is at present faced with the exertion of learners possessing hazardous armaments that could be employed to effortlessly commit malevolence acts. Fareo (2015) explicated that others are engaged in mob enrolment and enmity, massacre, rape, drug trafficking and other illegal actions. A quantity of these problems has resulted into sadistic acts within and around the school thus making school environment to turn out to be deadly in nature.

Security challenges cases have been generally accounted in lots of secondary schools both inside and outer the coast of Nigeria (Abdullahi & Terhemba, 2014). There are different types of security challenges which teachers, school management and parents are faced with in secondary schools, some of which includes vandalism, terrorism, extortion, fighting, cybercrime, bombing and bomb threats and kidnapping.

School security challenges are more common when there is no proper management of physical environment of the school, many hazards are bound to occur which can harm any member of the school community. The safety of staff, students, and every member of the school community has become an issue of concern which need to be addressed.

It has been observed that there is high rate of terrorism in the nation which has also degenerated into secondary schools. The activities of terrorist group appear to create fear into the lives of the teachers and students as well which result into poor teachers' effectiveness. Terrorism has severely affected the educational sector in Nigeria as a country. Nigeria is emerging country where virtually all segments of the nation are influenced by terrorism; yet the ruining consequence of terrorism on education is far more obvious. It was revealed from the study of Amanchukwu and Ololube (2015) that terrorism has brutally impacted the education at every level. It was also revealed that terrorism affect the spirit of the parents. Thus owing to the dread of terrorism, a number of parents are cautious to send their children to schools, thereby reducing in low enrolment of students in schools. Terrorism is an unexpected, planned violence and intimidation which ruins everything. Several incidents of terrorist's attacks on schooling/colleges/universities are documented, which has severely affected the stride of education development in the country.

Cultism has also been observed to be a security challenge affecting secondary school teachers' effectiveness. Cultism which refers to the activities of a small group of people which operations and membership are kept away from the knowledge of the public. The increase in intensity of cultism in secondary schools in the last few years could be regarded as a bad signal to the safety of teachers. The matter of cultism has in spite of many struggles at decreasing it, rose up in the Nigerian schools. Cultism is a security challenge which can greatly affect teacher effectiveness. Cultism has been known as a noticeable and challenging matter that reigned in most community. The fundamental problem of cultism is the uncertain and unsafe atmosphere in our schools across the strata of the society. People have complained that standard of education is falling very fast especially in our secondary schools,

they are of the point that the problem caused by cultism are very many and deadly. Any time the cultist struck there is always tension amongst the teacher's population as it leads to insecurity of life and properties.

Ajayi, Ekundayo and Osalusi (2010) revealed in their study on cultism threat in Nigerian tertiary institutions: the eccentric, that the key cultism causes in tertiary institutions were peer group sway, home milieu, communal profligacy, education benchmarks erosion, the Nigerian polity militarisation, poor recreational amenities, pursue for power and safety to mention a few. The persistent influence of cults has slowly penetrated the secondary school level where the related violence, torment, harassment and peer pressure linked with cultism have since found its way in Nigeria (Oragwu & Nwabueze, 2014)

It appears that any disruption resulting from security challenges may results in poor teacher effectiveness. For instance, if a teacher is trying to monitor the progress of students which are in any way connected to cultism he may be attacked by cultist, he will rather stop that act of monitoring students' progress to be safe and also if he is insisting on students being disciplined, he may also suffer from attack of cult groups, these among others may result in low job effectiveness.

Ajayi et al (2010) further revealed that the implication of cultism consists of academic conducts, loss of lives and possessions, insecure school settings to mention but a few. The cultists cause hazard to peace and safety in school environment and the larger community when cult clashes with one another. Therefore, where cult activities are prevalent teacher effectiveness seems to be low. Therefore, cultism is a contradiction and a deviation to the idea of education in Nigeria, which if not well managed may affect teacher effectiveness.

Safety indicates the condition of being sheltered, unharmed, hazard free, tenable, not involving danger. Every safety given to the youngster is to make him/her alive and protected. In a school environment, every student is entitled to safety from destruction, safety from mistreatment (e.g. rape), safety from illness, safety from undernourishment, safety from risky conduct, safety from physical cruelty and safety from road mishaps. A safe school refers to the place where learners can be given a premium education with no menace of brutality (Idoko, 2013).

School safety could be defined as a situation in which the teachers and learners feel at home, develop confidence, maintain a positive state of mind, and do not show any signs of withdrawal from the school, but work towards the achievement of their personal goals. Schools have to develop some active safety strategies that focus on general school climate in addition to emergency preparedness, and management of the school system. The security of the school environment and structures, involves certifying that edifices are secure for usage and that is particular to passages, staircases and porches where students walk to and from classes, and earlier in the school, vacant classrooms and outbuildings utilized for electrical fittings, storeroom, and some other service facilities (Schiffbauer, 2010).

Safety in the school is important to protect all students and school employees from aggressiveness that includes: attacks, mistreatment, harassment, theft, lecture hall disorder, fights, robbery, use of arms, sexual attacks, and fierce misconducts. The researcher however observed that some secondary schools appear not to be safe for academic staff to efficiently discharge their duty.

Several schools have building plans and strategies to execute secure school environment for quality job effectiveness (Oragwu & Nwabueze, 2014). These plans function most when they are engendered not merely by the personnel of the school, but as well by parents and agents from community groups and bodies. School insecurity could result to a disorderly and

intimidating setting, corporeal damage, and expressive strain, all of which can be impediments to teacher effectiveness (Isiugo-Abanihe & Labo-Popoola, 2004).

School safety is most illustrated by what a secure school is. As mentioned earlier, a secure school is that school that is physically and psycho-communally protected. Concerning the physical environment of the school, the main noticeable features of such kind are the value of the safety and the school buildings and grounds preservation. This denotes a dirt-free and safe environment that is favourable to teaching and has safekeeping possessions, well-cared for amenities, furnishings and utensils, hygienic toilets, water and green setting and deficiency of annoyance (Squelch, 2001).

As public concern has heightened following the rate of kidnapping, there is need for surveillance in our secondary schools. School surveillance involves observing the entire-school settings, taking obstructions from the school grounds, such as lack of windows, solid walls, bushes and trees, ensuring obvious visibility of major doorway(s), establishing parking parts so that they are evident, keeping vacant structures and entrances firmly locked, segregating "out of bounds" places, eradicating blind spots provided by doorways, buildings fences and landscaping, and control accessibility (Reid, 2000). According to Masitsa (2019), the most common use of a school video surveillance system is to amplify learner and staff security. Significantly placed cameras enlighten students and staff that they may possibly be watched which can dissuade laziness and bad behaviour which in turn can improve teacher effectiveness.

More so, cameras can grasp burglars, hooligans, and terrorists in the act. The surveillance cameras can be employed to watch every visitor to make sure they check in with the office catalogue and follow rules about contact to the students while in the campus. A correctly fitted school security system' cameras are vital device for ensuring security on the school ground. Masitsa (2019) reported that surveillance cameras is an obligatory aid to identify and resolving issues associated with violence, vandalism, theft among other security issues. Nwabueze (2016) found a positive relationship between school safety and teacher effectiveness. Chianu (2007) found out that school safety influence staff productivity. Oragwu and Nwabueze (2014) concluded that school safety is related to teacher effectiveness. Aluko (2012) and Idoko (2013) concluded that school safety will go a long way to improve job effectiveness.

The problem of this study is therefore to scrutinize how security challenges could affect secondary school teachers' effectiveness in Osun State. Specifically, the study examined:

1. the relationship between terrorism and secondary school teachers' effectiveness;
2. the relationship between cultism and secondary school teachers' effectiveness; and
3. the relationship between school safety and secondary school teachers' effectiveness.

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were generated for this study.

1. There is no significant relationship between terrorism and secondary school teachers' effectiveness in Osun State.
2. There is no significant relationship between cultism and secondary school teachers' effectiveness in Osun State.
3. There is no significant relationship between school safety and secondary school teachers' effectiveness in Osun State.

Methodology

The descriptive survey research and correlational research designs were used in this study. Descriptive research was considered suitable because, it emphasizes on the observation and

opinions of the existing situation. A survey research studies, a small sample from a large population from where inferences would be drawn about the characteristics of the defined population. It is correlational because the study intends to find out the correlation between variables of security challenges and teachers' effectiveness.

The population consisted of all teachers in public secondary schools in Osun State, Nigeria. The sample for this study consisted of 240 teachers in 24 public secondary schools in Osun State. Multi – stage sampling procedure was used in the selection of the sample for the study. In the first stage, 2 local government areas were selected from each senatorial districts using simple random sampling technique. The second stage involved the selection of 4 public secondary schools from each local government areas through stratified random sampling technique so that two urban and two rural schools were selected. The third involved the use of stratified random sampling technique to select 10 teachers from each of the sampled 24 schools. The principal of each selected schools were purposely selected through the use of purposive sampling technique to assess teachers' effectiveness.

Two self-designed research instruments tagged "Security Challenges Questionnaire (SCQ)" and "Teachers' Effectiveness Questionnaire (TEQ)" were used to collect relevant data for the study. Security Challenges Questionnaire was of two sections namely Section A and B. Section A of SCQ will seek for bio – data information of the respondents, section B will consist of 15 items to measure the sub-variables of security challenges namely: terrorism, cultism and school safety. Likert 4-point rating scale will be used as follows: Strongly Agree (SA) 4, Agree (A) 3, Disagree (D) 2 and Strongly Disagree (SD) 1. Teachers' Effectiveness Questionnaire was of three sections namely Section A, B and C. Section A of TEQ will seek for bio – data of the principals that will assess the teachers. Section B will seek for the bio-data of the teacher to be assessed while section C consists of 15 items measuring the teacher effectiveness. Likert 4-point rating scale will be adapted and used as follows: Excellent (E) 4, Good (G) 3, Fair (F) 2 and Poor (P) 1.

The validity of the instruments was ensured through face and content validity. The items in the questionnaire were presented to experts in the fields of Educational Management and Tests and Measurement. The experts checked the items and ascertain that they represented the variables and its adequacy to measure what it was meant for. The reliability of the instruments was determined by using test re-test reliability method. In doing this, the Security Challenges Questionnaire (SCQ) was administered on 20 teachers to answer SCQ and 2 principals to respond to Teachers' Effectiveness Questionnaire (TEQ) to assess the 20 teachers in 2 schools outside the schools that were sampled for the study. The instruments were administered twice within the interval of two weeks. In order to ascertain reliability of the instruments, data collected was analysed to obtain the reliability coefficients of the instruments using Pearson Product Moment Correlational analysis (PPMC) to obtain the reliability coefficient of the instruments. A reliability coefficient of 0.81 was obtained for SCQ while 0.77 was obtained for TEQ. The reliability coefficients were considered high enough for the reliability.

The instruments for the study were personally administered by the researcher with the aid of 2 trained research assistants. The data collected through the instruments were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using inferential statistics of Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC).

Results

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between terrorism and secondary school teachers' effectiveness in Osun State.

In testing this hypothesis, data on terrorism sub-variable of security challenges were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section B of SCQ (item 1 – 5) in the questionnaire. Data on teacher effectiveness were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section C of TEQ (item 1 – 15) in the questionnaire. Both were compared for statistical significance using Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 levels. The result was presented in table 1.

Table 1: Relationship between terrorism and teacher effectiveness

Variables	N	Mean	Stand Dev	r-cal	P-value
Terrorism	240	10.89	2.81	0.011	0.902
Teacher Effectiveness	240	49.20	3.48		

P>0.05

Table 1 showed that the r-cal value of 0.011 was not significant at 0.05 level of significance because the P-value (0.902) > 0.05. The null hypothesis was not rejected. This implied that there was no significant relationship between terrorism and secondary school teachers' effectiveness in Osun State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between cultism and secondary school teachers' effectiveness in Osun State.

In testing this hypothesis, data on cultism sub-variable of security challenges were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section B of SCQ (item 6 – 10) in the questionnaire. Data on teacher effectiveness were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section C of TEQ (item 1 – 15) in the questionnaire. Both were compared for statistical significance using Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 levels. The result was presented in table 2.

Table 2: Relationship between cultism and teacher effectiveness

Variables	N	Mean	Stand Dev	r-cal	P-value
Cultism	240	14.20	3.06	-0.412*	0.00
Teacher Effectiveness	240	49.20	3.48		

*P<0.05

Table 2 showed that the r-cal value of -0.412 was significant at 0.05 level of significance because the P-value (0.000) < 0.05. The null hypothesis was rejected. This implied that there was significant relationship between cultism and secondary school teachers' effectiveness in Osun State. However, there was negative relationship between cultism and teachers' effectiveness, which implies that high rate of cultism will reduce the level of teachers' effectiveness

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between school safety and secondary school teachers' effectiveness in Osun State.

In testing this hypothesis, data on school safety sub-variable of security challenges were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section B of SCQ (item 11 – 15) in the questionnaire. Data on teacher effectiveness were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section C of TEQ (item 1 – 15) in the questionnaire. Both were compared for statistical significance using Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 levels. The result was presented in table 3.

Table 3: Relationship between school safety and teacher effectiveness

Variables	N	Mean	Stand Dev	r-cal	P-value
School Safety	240	14.93	3.71	0.607*	0.00
Teacher Effectiveness	240	49.20	3.48		

*P<0.05

Table 3 showed that the r-cal value of 0.607 was significant at 0.05 level of significance because the P-value (0.000) < 0.05. The null hypothesis was rejected. This implied that there was significant relationship between school safety and secondary school teachers' effectiveness in Osun State.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that there was no significant relationship between terrorism and secondary school teachers' effectiveness in Osun State. The findings of Nwabueze (2016) revealed that terrorism effect increases with the number of mortalities and decreases with the physical distance between the teachers and the attack location which may not affect their effectiveness.

The study however revealed that there was significant negative relationship between cultism and secondary school teachers' effectiveness in Osun State. It is inferred that cultism could negatively have impact on teachers' effectiveness. The implication of this finding is that if security measures to curb cultism are put in place, teachers' effectiveness will be effective and efficient. The probable reason for this finding could be as a result of the importance of putting in place security measures to curb cultism. This result is consistent with previous findings of other scholars such as Udoh and Ikezi (2015) that cultism affects the institution extremely, both in standard of education and in discipline. Also Xaba (2015), revealed that effect of cultism include loss of lives and properties, disruption of academic activities on campuses, unsafe school environments among others.

It was also revealed that there was significant relationship between school safety and secondary school teachers' effectiveness in Osun State. It could be inferred that there will be improvement in teacher effectiveness if safety of school is prioritised. The probable reason for this finding could be due to the fact that effective teaching and learning could only take place in a safe environment, if the schools are not safe it will be difficult for teachers to discharge their duties thereby compromising job effectiveness. This finding is in consonance with Nwabueze (2016), Oragwu and Nwabueze (2014), Idoko (2013) and Aluko (2012) who found a significant relationship between school safety and job effectiveness.

Conclusion

Sequel to the findings of this study, it was concluded that security challenges such as cultism and school safety determined the effectiveness of teachers in secondary schools.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Conferences, seminars and workshop should be regularly organized for all teachers to broaden their knowledge and familiarise them with current innovations in security procedure.
2. There should be a policy and regulations against cultism in secondary schools which must be adequately enforced to maintain a safe and secured school environment

3. Secondary school management should install Closed Circuit Television (CCTV) at strategic places to monitor activities of staff and students for possible discovery of criminal events within the school compound.
4. Security is everyone's concern, therefore, it is necessary for security consciousness by teachers and students in order to stay secured.

References

- Abdullahi, U and Terhemba, G. A. (2014). Influence of insecurity on Primary School Attendance in Damaturu Metropolis, Yobe State Nigeria. *Journal of Research in Education and Society*, 5(1) 33-38.
- Amanchukwu, R. N. and Ololube, N. P. (2015). Managing School Plant for Effective Service Delivery in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State of Nigeria. *Journal of Human Resource Management Research*. 5(4): 95-102.
- Bassey, S. U. & Bassey, U. U. (2008). Perceived resource availability and job performance among teachers in Akwa-Ibom and Cross River States of Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Society*. 6(1), 1-8.
- Chianu, E. (2007). *Corporal punishment in primary and secondary schools: The legal position*. Asaba: Publishers Endless Book
- Ebeniza, A.N & Ukegbu, M. N. (2015). Web-based tools and instructional delivery in selected secondary schools in owerri education zone 1, Imo State, *International Letters of Social and Humanistic Sciences*, 55, 1-6.
- Fareo, D. O. (2015). Bullying in Nigeria Secondary School: Strategies for Counselling Intervention. <http://www.ojjdp.ncjrs.org/> Retrieved 24/7/2019
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014). *National policy on education*. Lagos: NERDC
- Idoko, A.A. (2013). *Understanding school management*. Makurdi: Ugo printing press.
- Isiugo-Abanihe, I. & Labo-Popoola O. S. (2004). School type and location as environmental factors in learning English as a second language. *West African Journal of Education*, 23(1), 55-71.
- Masitsa, M. G. (2019). Exploring Students' Safety in Township Secondary Schools in the Free State Providence. *South Africa Journal of Education*, 7(1), 78 – 84
- Meiers, M. (2007). Teacher Professional Learning, Teaching Practice and Student Learning outcome: Important Issues. In T. Townsend & R. Bates (Eds.), *Handbook Of Teacher Education: Globalization, Standards and Professionalism in Times of Change* (pp. 409-414). Netherlands: Springer
- Nwabueze, A.I. (2016). Influence of Teaching/Learning Environment on the Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in South-East, Nigeria. *African Journal of Education, Research and Development*, 15(1), 228 – 234
- Okolie, U.C. (2014). Management of school administration in secondary schools in Nigeria: An analytical study. *Malaysian Online Journal of Education*, 2(1), 20-36.
- Okolocha, C.C. & Onyeneke, E.N. (2013). Secondary school principals' perception of teachers' teaching effectiveness in Anambra State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 4 (2), 171-182.
- Olofin, S.O. and Olojo, O.J. (2022). Effect of Brain-based Strategy on Senior Secondary School Students' Performance in Mathematics in Ekiti State. *International Journal of Education, Learning and Development*, 10(2), 1 – 15. DOI: doi.org/10.37745/ijeld.13/vol10no2pp.1-15

- Oluchukwu (2010). Challenges of Educational Planning in the 21st Century: In Olagboye, A.A. Fadipe, J.O. (Eds) *Management of Nigerian Education: School Project Monitoring and School Plant Maintenance*. NIEPA, Ondo.
- Oragwu, A. & Nwabueze, A. I. (2014). Employee Safety, School Environment and Quality Teaching in South-East Universities. *African Journal of Higher Education Studies and Development*, 5(2), 103 - 114
- Ornstein, A. C., & Lunenburg, F. C. (2008). *Educational administration: Concepts and practices*. Thomson Higher Education.
- Reid, D. (2000). Building a safe environment. *American School & University*, 1.
- Schiffbauer, P. (2010). A checklist for safe schools. *Educational Leadership*.
- Squelch, J. (2001). Do school governing bodies have a duty to create safe schools? An educational law perspective. *Perspectives in Education*, 19(1), 137-149.
- Trump K. (2010). *Education department redefines safety*. Retrieved on March 30 2021 from <http://www.schoolsecurityblog.com/2010/8/ec>
- Xaba, M. I. (2015). A qualitative analysis of facilities maintenance: A School governance function in South Africa. *South African Journal of Education*, 32(2), 215-226.

Cite this article:

Author(s), ODEDIJI, Kehinde Morufdeen And OLOFIN, Samuel Oluwaseyi (Ph.D), (2023). "Security Challenges and Secondary School Teachers' Effectiveness in Osun State, Nigeria". Name of the Journal: International Journal of Academic Research in Business, Arts and Science, (IJARBAS.COM), P, 1-11 , DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7644490> , Issue: 1, Vol.: 5, Article: 1, Month: January, Year: 2023. Retrieved from <https://www.ijarbas.com/all-issues/>

Published by

AND

ThoughtWares Consulting & Multi Services International ([TWCMSI](https://www.thoughtwares.com))

